

Magnetic quadrupole-exciton, electric dipole-exciton, and anapole-exciton interaction mediated resonance energy transfer in Mie-exciton heterostructure

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Abstract

Controlling and comprehending light-matter interaction at the nanoscale constitutes a central objective due to its applications in nanophotonic devices and quantum information processing. This study presents numerical simulations focused on Mie-exciton heterostructures, specifically investigating the mode coupling between electric dipole (ED)-exciton, magnetic quadrupole (MQ)-exciton, and anapole mode (AM)-exciton. The Mie resonance modes originate from a high-index silicon (Si) nanosphere resonator, while the exciton is derived from a WS₂ monolayer. The light-matter interaction between Si and WS₂ monolayer leads to mode hybridization and resonance

coupling. By employing the classical coupled oscillator model and calculating Hopfield coefficients, strong coupling between modes is demonstrated. The results exhibit an intriguing anti-crossing behavior, providing compelling evidence of the strong coupling between Mie resonances and exciton resonances. Moreover, we explore the influence of the number of monolayers and the size of the Si nano-resonator on mode hybridization and resonance coupling. Our findings reveal that the coupling strength and coherent energy transfer between different modes are highly sensitive to both the number of WS₂ monolayers and the size of the Si nano-resonator. The insights gained from this research hold significant promise for the advancement of polariton-exciton nanodevices and quantum technologies.

Keywords

Strong resonance coupling, mode hybridization, Mie-exciton heterostructure, magnetic quadrupole, Electric dipole, Exciton, Silicon nanosphere, WS₂ monolayer.

Introduction

The robust interaction between quantum emitters and photons via strong coupling produces qubits, which are essential for quantum communication and computing as they facilitate the transmission of quantum information over long distances and allow for ultrafast signal processing [1-3]. In recent years researchers have focused on studying strong coupling thoroughly to establish a quantum network by integrating multiple qubits, which enables the efficient manipulation of quantum states through the use of photonic elements, unlocking a wide range of scientific and technological frontiers [4-6]. Strong coupling via resonance also enables major implications in various applications, including exciton-polariton lasers, ultrafast optical

switching, quantum manipulation, coherent emission or absorption, and all-optical logic devices [7-10]. Mode coupling and quantized quenching arise due to the result of the interaction between the optical resonator and quantum emitters [11]. This coupling mechanism enables coherent and reversible transfer of energy during the spectrally overlapped resonator and emitter interaction [12]. The attainment of a strong coupling regime between the resonator and resonant excitons occurs when the rate of energy exchange between the two subsystems surpasses their respective energy decay rates [13]. This is facilitated by the transition dipole moment (μ) of excitons, which strongly influences mode splitting and quantized quenching dips observed on the optical extinction or scattering spectra [12]. A higher value of μ leads to a stronger light-matter interaction, and in this regard, TMDCs exhibit a larger μ value compared to dye molecules, quantum dots, *J*-aggregates, and quantum wells-based emitters. Also, TMDCs have recently demonstrated the ability to overcome existing challenges such as exciton bleaching, the limited thermal stability of excitons, and the strong localization effect of disordered potentials in hybrid systems [14]. Additionally, the direct bandgaps and high absorptivity with narrow line widths of TMDCs offer further advantages for their utilization in exciton-polariton coupling [15]. Atomically thin single-layered (1L) two-dimensional TMDCs belong to the van der Waals stacked crystals family, represented by the common chemical formula MX_2 (transition metals M: Mo and W, and chalcogen element X: S, and Se) [16,17], consists of a hexagonal arrangement of transition metal atoms embedded between two hexagonal lattices of chalcogenide atoms. The bandgap of TMDCs lies in the visible to near IR range and the bandgap property (from indirect to direct transition) can be tailored by reducing the thickness to a monolayer [18]. Among these TMDCs, monolayer WS_2 has garnered increasing attention due to its exceptional properties, including significant spin-orbit coupling, thickness-dependent optical properties, the high quantum yield of emission, large binding energies of excitons and trions, as well as nonblinking photon emission [17].

Nanostructures with high refractive index are considered optical resonators as they can confine the light at the nanoscale and these types of materials show small imaginary dielectric functions in contrast to the plasmonic materials in broadband spectral region [19,20]. The optical response of subwavelength high refractive index particles is determined by the oscillation of induced polarization charges and circular displacement current inside the nanocavity helps to generate electric and magnetic multipoles [19]. In contrast for plasmonic nanostructure, free charge carriers are crucial for optical resonance mode localization. Recently, the optical properties of high index nanostructures which can easily produce different resonant multipole modes become interesting due to the application point of view, even though all these phenomena are quite well-known through Mie scattering theory [21]. In this context, Si is one of the widely studied Mie-resonators due to its high refractive index, low absorption at near-infrared frequencies, scattering light directionality, and the possibility to concentrate the electric field without Joule losses [22,23].

Recently, different types of resonance coupling mediated energy transfer reported to study the light-matter interaction between optical nano-resonators and 2D TMDCs such as plasmon-exciton coupling [24], plasmon-exciton-trion coupling [25], magnetic dipole-exciton coupling [26], and so on [27-32]. The main disadvantage observed for the plasmon-exciton coupling system is that all-plasmonic nanostructures generate a large amount of heating, which can damage the surface of 2D material. Therefore, all-dielectric nanostructures are used to overcome such limitations, which have small mode volume and negligible loss.

In this present work, we have focused on the Si nanosphere wrapped with WS₂ monolayer and as a result Mie scattering modes (such as electric dipole, magnetic dipole, electric quadrupole, magnetic quadrupole: ED, MD, EQ, MQ) directly interact with exciton originated from monolayer of WS₂. There are some reports present in the literature where the Si-WS₂ combination was used for resonance coupling. Recently, Lepeshov et al. and Wang et al. reported the strong coupling achieved via magnetic dipole-exciton coupling in the Si-WS₂ nanosystem [12,33].

Herein, we demonstrated the strong coupling between ED-exciton, AM-exciton, and MQ-exciton mode coupling where ED, AM, and MQ belong to the Mie resonance modes originated from Si nanosphere and exciton from WS_2 monolayer in the hybrid heterostructure system. To the best of our knowledge, it is the first report on MQ-exciton resonance coupling mediated energy exchange between high index nanostructure and TMDC. The resonance coupling is demonstrated by the classical coupled oscillator model followed by the calculations of Hopfield coefficients. The ED-exciton and anapole exciton coupling are also presented in a similar structure and it is to be noted here that the coupling is mostly dependent on the radius of the Si nanocavity. Moreover, to understand the effect of WS_2 monolayer on resonance coupling and mode hybridization we have carried out all the calculations for single and three monolayers (1L and 3L) of WS_2 .

Methodology

Electromagnetic simulations: In this study, we employed the finite element method (FEM) for modeling and conducting numerical simulations using the commercial software package COMSOL Multiphysics V6.0. To estimate the scattering efficiency of the single Si- WS_2 nanostructure, we utilized the frequency domain FEM solver within the wave optics module. Throughout the simulations, the nanoparticles were positioned at the center of the simulation domain, with the surrounding host matrix set as air (refractive index of 1). Illumination of the nanoparticles was achieved using a plane wave, with a fixed incident electric field amplitude of 1 V/m, used for all the near-field calculations. To minimize undesired reflections and backscattering from the numerical boundaries, we implemented a spherical type perfectly matched layer (PML) of appropriate dimensions. Inside the PML, free tetrahedral meshing with finer geometry was utilized. The simulations were executed using a direct stationary solver. For obtaining the wavelength-dependent refractive index of Si [34], we referred to the optical material library integrated into COMSOL software. Additionally, we calculated the scattering spectra employing multipolar decomposition (details can be found in Ref. 35), while the absorption spectra were

estimated by integrating the power loss density over the volumes [26, 36]. Detailed information regarding the dielectric functions of the other materials utilized in simulations can be found in the results and discussions section.

Results and discussions

The system under theoretical study consists of an isolated heterostructure created by crystalline silicon (Si) nanosphere coated with WS₂ monolayer as shown in the schematic of Fig. 1. Crystalline Si has a high refractive index and adequate losses in the visible region, different literature already claimed about the synthesis of such shape either by wet chemistry method or femtosecond laser ablation [13,22]. Si nanosphere coated with ultrathin WS₂ monolayer heterostructure can be possible to fabricated in many experimental ways. For example, very recently Hinamoto et. al. reported resonance coupling in standalone (substrate-free) Si-MoS₂ core-shell nanostructure, where the heterostructure was fabricated in the bottom-up method using chemical vapor deposition technique [37]. Panel (a) of Fig. 1 depicts a physical model with a two-level energy system where the ground and excited state of exciton from 2D material (WS₂) is represented by $|g\rangle$ and $|e\rangle$, separated by band gap energy. When the plane wave incident on Si nanosphere, due to the separation of positive and negative electric charges ED is created. Anapole mode (AM) appears for destructive interference between electric and toroidal dipoles with opposite phases and the same amplitude. The MQ mode has unique characteristics compared to other Mie resonance modes, the magnetic field exhibits a complex pattern with two poles of opposite sign along the diameter of the particle, creating a quadrupolar distribution. $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ in panel (a) of Fig. 1 represent unexcited and resonance Mie scattering modes (ED/AM/MQ). The interaction between Mie resonance modes and excitonic transition modes helps to create mode hybridization via spectral overlapping, as shown in panel (b). These interactions enable hybrid energy state separated by large Rabi splitting energy (upper energy

branch; UEB & lower energy branch; LEB), which correspond to the coherent energy exchange between Si nanosphere and WS_2 monolayer as shown in the schematic of the panel (a), Fig. 1. Panel (c) of Fig. 1 illustrate the assumption that Si- WS_2 nanostructure is the summation of isolated Si nanosphere as core and hollow WS_2 as 2D monolayer shell. Therefore, the Mie-exciton coupling modes can be treated as the superposition output from Mie-type modes originating from Si core and exciton modes originating from the WS_2 shell.

The real and imaginary part of the refractive index of the monolayer WS_2 (1L- WS_2) was taken from Ref. [14]. The orange curve in panel (d) of Fig. 1 represents the normalized absorption efficiency (Q_{abs}) spectrum of 1L- WS_2 (air is inside and outside), where the absorption maxima (611.5 nm) represent the A - excitonic transition, originated due to direct gap transitions at the K -valley of the Brillouin zone [15]. The ED and MQ contribution in the scattering efficiency spectrum (Q_{sca}) of isolated Si nanosphere and Si nanosphere with 1L- WS_2 coating in air medium is shown as black, blue, red, and green curve respectively in Panel (d) of Fig. 1. The hybridization of the Mie resonance peak (red and green curve) observed in case of Si nanosphere with 1L- WS_2 coating, whereas mode splitting is not observed in case of Si nanosphere. It represents the interaction via energy exchange between Mie resonance modes from high refractive index Si nanosphere and exciton from 2D semiconductor material. Another Mie resonance modes (MD and EQ) are not included in the figure as the exciton does not influence the spectrum at all or it was completely uncoupled with exciton mode.

Fig. 1: Panel (a) shows the schematic illustration of the energy level diagram of Si-WS₂ heterostructure and the formation of new hybrid state with Rabi splitting energy, originating due to the interaction between Mie resonance modes from Si nanosphere and exciton from WS₂ monolayer. Panel (b) shows the schematic of different Mie resonance modes (ED, MQ, and anapole) interacting with exciton, producing UEB and LEB in scattering spectra by hybridization of resonance modes. Panel (c) shows the assumption that the scattering spectra of Si-WS₂ heterostructure are the summation of Si nanosphere and hollow WS₂ monolayer. Panels (d) represent the simulated efficiency spectrum of Si nanosphere with and without WS₂ monolayer. Green and blue curves are the MQ spectrum of Si nanosphere with and without WS₂ monolayer, whereas red and black curves are the ED spectrum of Si nanosphere with and without WS₂ monolayer, respectively. The orange spectrum represents the normalized Q_{abs} spectrum of a hollow WS₂ monolayer.

In Fig. 2, panels (a), (c), and (e) display a color-mapped spectrum of Q_{abs} , while panels (b), (d), and (f) present Q_{sca} for an isolated Si nanosphere, Si-WS₂ (1L), and Si-WS₂ (3L) heterostructures, respectively. The spectral data were obtained by varying the radius of Si nanosphere within the range of 90 nm to 115 nm. The isolated Si nanosphere exhibits typical Q_{abs} and Q_{sca} spectra. However, the introduction of a WS₂ monolayer has induced noticeable coupling between the Mie resonance mode and the exciton, evident in both Q_{abs} and Q_{sca} spectra. Here,

Si-WS₂ behaves as a Mie-exciton heterostructure, displaying an anti-crossing behavior in both Q_{abs} and Q_{sca} spectra (the white dotted box in the Q_{sca} spectra). This affirms a strong interaction between Mie resonance modes from the Si nanosphere and exciton modes from WS₂. Furthermore, this coupling is directly influenced by the radius of Si nanosphere and the number of WS₂ monolayers. As we know, the Q_{sca} spectrum is the aggregate of ED, MD, EQ, and MQ modes, some of which contribute to Mie-exciton interaction. Our current study primarily focuses on investigating the interaction between MQ-exciton, ED-exciton, and anapole-exciton modes, including their mode-hybridization and resonance coupling. To gain a deeper understanding of the involved physics, we conducted detailed numerical simulations on Si nanospheres coated with a monolayer (1L) and three layers (3L) of WS₂ using plane wave illumination. These numerical simulations aim to achieve the following objectives: (i) identify the specific Mie resonance mode interacting with the exciton mode, (ii) comprehend the nature of the coupling, and (iii) evaluate the impact of the radius of Si nanosphere and the number of WS₂ monolayers.

Fig. 2: Panels (a) and (b) display the spectrum mapping of Q_{abs} and Q_{sca} for an isolated Si nanosphere in the air medium. Panels (c) and (d) exhibit the spectrum mapping of Q_{abs} and Q_{sca} for Si nanosphere-WS₂

(1L) heterostructure, whereas panels (e) and (f) demonstrate the spectrum mapping of Q_{abs} and Q_{sca} for Si nanosphere-WS₂ (3L) heterostructure in the air medium. The radius of the Si nanosphere was varied from 90 nm to 115 nm. The white dotted lines represent the exciton mode resulting from WS₂, while the white color dotted boxes show the anti-crossing behavior representing the Mie-exciton mode coupling.

The black and red curve in Fig. 3 represent the MQ contribution in the Q_{sca} spectrum due to the effect of 1L ($r_{Si}=107$ nm) and 3L-WS₂ ($r_{Si}=104$ nm), respectively. Hybridization of mode is observed in both cases, representing the energy exchange via light-matter interaction. The hybridized modes are divided into UEB and LEB (represented by green and blue color), as shown in Fig. 3. The insets of Fig. 3 show the near field distribution at resonance wavelength of the Si-WS₂ heterostructure for single and three layers of WS₂, where the field is trapped inside represent the typical MQ resonance mode. (i) and (iii) represent the local magnetic field enhancement ($|H/H_0|$) corresponding to the MQ mode of UEB whereas (ii) and (iv) represent the LEB polaritons.

Fig. 3: Panel (a) shows the MQ resonance contribution in the scattering efficiency spectrum of Si-WS₂ heterostructure. Here the red and black curves were simulated with single (1) and three (3) monolayers of WS₂ respectively. The blue and green colors correspond to the LEB and UEB. Panels (b) and (c) show the near-field distribution of the resonance peaks of MQ modes.

The mode hybridization depicted in Fig. 3 easily induces strong coupling and it will satisfy these conditions as follows: (a) the anti-crossing behavior observed in the energy diagram, (b) $2|g| > \left| \frac{\Gamma_{Mie} - \Gamma_{exc}}{2} \right|$; represent non-vanishing criteria and (c) $\Omega_R > \frac{\Gamma_{Mie}}{2} + \frac{\Gamma_{exc}}{2}$; represent the value of Rabi splitting is larger than the full-width half maximum of the Mie resonance modes (MQ/ED/AM) and exciton modes. The strong coupling in any system can only be observed spectrally when all these conditions are fulfilled simultaneously [38]. Γ_{Mie} , Γ_{exc} , g , and Ω_R represent the line width of the Mie resonance mode (MQ/ED/AM), the line width of the exciton mode, coupling strength of the hybrid system and Rabi splitting, respectively. When all the above-mentioned conditions are satisfied, then the energy exchange rate between the Mie mode and exciton mode should exceed their individual rate of decay [39].

The classical coupled harmonic oscillator model (COM) is used to explain the origin of mode hybridization and calculate the values of g , and Ω_R for the MQ and exciton interaction in Si-WS₂ heterostructure, where the overall hybridized system was imagined as two coupled harmonic oscillator systems [13].

$$\begin{pmatrix} E_{Mie} - i\Gamma_{Mie}/2 & \Omega_R/2 \\ \Omega_R/2 & E_{exc} - i\Gamma_{exc}/2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{pmatrix} = E \begin{pmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Here, E_{Mie} and E_{exc} are the resonance energy of the Mie resonance modes and the exciton mode, respectively. E are the eigenvalues that are related to the energies of the new hybridized states, and α and β are known as Hopfield coefficients or UEB and LEB hybrid states that represent the energy exchange behavior between different Mie resonant modes and exciton modes. The hybrid state should satisfy the condition of $|\alpha|^2 + |\beta|^2 = 1$; which is nothing but the weighting coefficients of the fraction of Mie resonance mode (MQ/ED/AM) and exciton mode. The Hopfield coefficients can be determined using the following formula [40],

$$\alpha_{UEB} = \beta_{LEB} = \frac{(E_{Mie} - E_{exc}) + \sqrt{(E_{Mie} - E_{exc})^2 + \Omega_R^2}}{2\sqrt{(E_{Mie}^2 - E_{exc}^2)^2 + \Omega_R^2}} \quad (2)$$

$$\alpha_{LEB} = \beta_{UEB} = 1 - \alpha_{UEB} \quad (3)$$

The energy of the hybrid state ($E_{UEB/LEB}$) can be expressed as,

$$E_{UEB/LEB} = \frac{1}{2}(E_{Mie} + E_{exc}) \pm \sqrt{g^2 + 0.25 \left((E_{Mie} - E_{exc}) - \frac{i}{2}(\Gamma_{Mie} - \Gamma_{exc}) \right)^2} \quad (4)$$

$(E_{Mie} - E_{exc})$ is known as detuning energy between Mie resonance mode (MQ/ED/AM) and exciton mode. The coupling characteristics of MQ and exciton modes are evaluated using the above formulas and the values are tabulated in Table 1. From Table 1, we can conclude that both the heterostructures follow the strong coupling criteria. By increasing the monolayer of WS₂ from 1 to 3, the line width of MQ-based Mie resonance mode increases, or broadening in MQ spectra is observed. Also, the Rabi splitting energy increases due to the increase in the number of WS₂ layers.

Table 1: Calculated parameters using COM approximation

Heterostructure	E_{Mie}	E_{exc}	Γ_{Mie}	Γ_{exc}	$\frac{\Gamma_{Mie}}{2} + \frac{\Gamma_{exc}}{2}$	Ω_R
Si : 1L-WS ₂	2.054 eV	2.004 eV	37.79 meV	35.44 meV	36.61 meV	49.35 meV
Si : 3L-WS ₂	2.072 eV	1.993 eV	41.11 meV	29.69 meV	35.4 meV	78.63 meV

Panel (a) of Fig. 4 shows the MQ contribution in Q_{sca} spectrum of Si-WS₂ (1L) heterostructure, where the radius of the Si nanosphere varied from 100 nm to 115 nm. Similarly, panel (b) of Fig. 4 shows the MQ spectrum of Si nanosphere coated with 3L-WS₂ with the variation of radius from 90 nm to 115 nm. These plots reveal the effect of the radius of the Si nanosphere as well as the number of layers on MQ spectrum. Mode hybridization in the scattering spectrum was observed for both 1L and 3L-WS₂, due to the energy exchange between Mie resonance modes and exciton, however, their shape and nature are different. In both cases, the resonance is red-shifted by increasing the value of r_{Si} . Panels (c) and (d) of Fig. 4 show the Q_{sca} spectrum color map as a function of r_{Si} , plotted for Si-WS₂ (1L) and Si-WS₂ (3L) systems, respectively. The

obtained results from both the color-map reveal the expected anti-crossing behavior, which was further confirmed by panels (a) and (b) of Fig. 5. In Fig. 5, the energy values or the peak position as a function of r_{Si} are extracted from panels (a) and (b) of Fig. 4. In both the cases (1L and 3L WS_2) anti-crossing behavior was observed between UEB and LEB which represent the reversible coherent energy exchange. These results are clear evidence of strong coupling between MQ and exciton. However, the values of Rabi splitting energy is different, which indicates the coupling strength can be tailored by using the different number of WS_2 monolayer. We have also calculated the Hopfield coefficient using the equation (2) and (3) and illustrated in panels (c) to (f) of Fig. 5 for 1L and 3L WS_2 , respectively. In both cases (1L and 3L WS_2), the value of the coefficient is close to 0.5 at resonance, which indicates the complete formation of an eigen hybrid state via light-matter interaction.

Fig. 4: Panels (a) and (b) show the MQ resonance response in scattering spectrum of Si- WS_2 (1L) and Si- WS_2 (3L), respectively. The plots are constructed by varying the radius of the Si nanosphere (r_{Si}). To confirm the anti-crossing behavior we have plotted the colormap of scattering efficiency, where panels (c) and (d) correspond to the Si- WS_2 (1L) and Si- WS_2 (3L) heterostructure, respectively.

Fig. 5: Panels (a) and (b) show the comparison of peak positions of the simulated scattering spectra, extracted from Fig. 3, where red dots and blue dots represent the UEB and LEB of Si-WS₂ (1L) and Si-WS₂ (3L), respectively. Black arrow, green and purple dotted lines in both cases represent the Rabi splitting energy, exciton, and MQ resonance modes, respectively. Panels (c)-(f) show the calculated Hopfield coefficients of the UEB and LEB for Si-WS₂ (1L) and Si-WS₂ (3L), respectively.

In this section, we will discuss the exciton interaction with ED and AM in the Si-WS₂ heterostructure and explore their strong coupling nature. We have already discussed the formation of AM earlier, and such a mode always creates a dip in the Q_{sca} spectra, helping us to be recognized with ease [13]. Panel (a) of Fig. 6 shows the ED contribution in Q_{sca} spectra for Si-WS₂ (1L) heterostructure, where r_{Si} is varied from 100 to 115 nm. Hybridization of modes in the scattering spectrum is observed due to the coating of 1L-WS₂ and the hybridized modes correspond to the UEB and LEB. Such hybridization appeared due to the interaction between Mie resonance modes (either ED or AM) from Si nanocavity and exciton from 1L-WS₂. The corresponding dips, peaks, dips, and peaks are represented by a_1 , a_2 , a_3 , and a_4 respectively distributed from higher energy to lower energy, shown as green lines in the scattering spectra. These modes are represented as the new hybrid state originated due to the interaction between

either ED and exciton or AM and exciton. By increasing the value of r_{Si} , the scattering volume of the Mie resonator cavity is increasing and the formation of hybrid states is blue-shifted in the wavelength scale. We have plotted separately the ED response in case of $r_{Si} = 100$ nm (black) and 113 nm (red), shown in panel (b) of Fig. 6. It is to be noted that the monolayer exciton influences the ED mode for a smaller value of r_{Si} , e.g. uncoupled AM and ED-exciton coupling is observed for $r_{Si} = 100$ nm. In contrast, exciton starts to couple with AM, due to the increase of the value of r_{Si} , e.g. uncoupled ED and AM-exciton coupling is observed for $r_{Si} = 113$ nm. The inset of panel (b) shows the magnified section of two scattering dips, which is evidence of AM-exciton coupling. The corresponding near-field distributions are shown as insets close to the peak and dip area in panel (b). The electric field distributions are trapped inside the cavity due to the dominance of AM (shown in (i), (ii), and (iv)), whereas in the case of ED the electric field is observed on the surface of Si-WS₂ (1L) heterostructure (shown in (iii), (v) and (vi)).

Panel (c) of Fig. 6 shows the ED contribution in scattering spectrum color-map plotted in energy scale where the value of r_{Si} varied from 100 to 115 nm. The corresponding peaks and dips in the new hybrid state are shown by dotted lines and represent the energy exchange between exciton and Mie resonance modes (in this case either ED or AM). To understand further we have plotted the hybrid modes (a_1 , a_2 , a_3 , and a_4) by varying the values of r_{Si} and shown in panel (d) of Fig. 6, by extracting the resonant energies from panel (a) of Fig. 6. In the absence of 1L-WS₂, only two mode is observed: a_1 and a_4 representing the non-radiating AM, and ED modes, which are red-shifted due to increase of r_{Si} . The remaining modes or hybridized modes are only visible by introducing the 1L WS₂. The black arrow in panel (d) represents the Rabi splitting energy can be expressed as the energy difference between UEB and LEB. From panel (d) we can conclude the following points: (i) The hybrid states exhibit the anti-crossing behavior due to the coupling between ED and exciton for smaller values of r_{Si} and also in this region exciton is completely uncoupled with AM (highlighted as brown color in panel (d) of Fig. 6). (ii) On the other hand for larger values of r_{Si} , exciton is coupling with AM represented by anti-crossing behavior (highlighted

as light-red color in panel (d) of Fig. 6). (iii) the anti-crossing behavior reflects the strong coupling nature upon the energy exchange via light-matter interaction for Si-WS₂ (1L) heterostructures, produces two scattering dips corresponds to UEB and LEB.

Fig. 6: Panel (a) shows the ED resonance response in scattering spectrum of Si-WS₂ (1L). The plots are constructed by varying the radius of the Si nanosphere (r_{Si}) from 100 nm to 115 nm. To understand the coupling between ED-exciton, AM-exciton, uncoupled ED, and uncoupled AM, we have plotted separately

the scattering spectrum with $r_{Si} = 100$ nm (black), and 113 nm (red), as shown in panel (b) respectively. Also, the inset shows the magnified section of the AM-exciton coupling and all the near-field distribution at the resonance. Panel (c) shows a color-map of ED contribution in Q_{sca} as a function of energy and r_{Si} , which confirm the anti-crossing behavior. Panel (d) shows the peak positions of the simulated scattering spectra, where the resonant energy values of the hybrid modes are extracted from panel (a) of Fig. 6.

To explore the effect of the number of monolayer of 2D-WS₂ on light-matter interaction, we have performed the numerical simulations where 3 monolayer (3L) was used. Panel (a) of Fig. 7 shows the ED contribution in Q_{sca} spectra for Si-WS₂ (3L) heterostructure, where r_{Si} is varied from 90 to 114 nm. The hybrid modes are formed due to the energy transfer between Mie modes (either ED or AM) and exciton from 3L-WS₂. The modes here are indexed as a_1 , a_2 , a_3 , and a_4 respectively distributed from higher energy to lower energy, shown as green lines in the scattering spectra. Like the previous case, here corresponding dips, peaks, dips, and peaks are represented by a_1 , a_2 , a_3 , and a_4 respectively distributed in the scattering spectra. Furthermore, we have plotted separately the ED contribution for $r_{Si} = 90$ nm, 95 nm, 100 nm, and 115 nm respectively as shown in panel (b) of Fig. 7. We can conclude the following points from panel (b): (i) For larger values of r_{Si} , AM-exciton coupling, and uncoupled ED are observed, whereas ED-exciton coupling happens in comparatively smaller values of r_{Si} . (ii) In the case of $r_{Si} = 90$ nm, weak ED-exciton coupling is observed, by increasing the value of r_{Si} strong coupling takes place. Similar behavior in the case of AM-exciton is also observed, which means the mode hybridization and energy exchange between Mie modes and excitons are very sensitive to the values of r_{Si} . In other words, the coupling between Mie resonance modes and exciton can be tailored easily from scattering state to non-scattering state by simply changing the values of r_{Si} . (iii) The mode hybridizations are blue-shifted in wavelength scale due to the increase of the value r_{Si} .

The ED contribution in the scattering spectrum by varying the values of r_{Si} from 90 to 115 nm is represented via a color-map plot as shown in panel (c) of Fig. 7. The corresponding peaks and dips in the new hybrid state are shown by dotted lines, represent the energy exchange between exciton and Mie resonance modes (in this case either ED or AM). To explore the anti-

crossing behavior of Si-WS₂ (3L) heterostructures further, we have plotted the hybrid modes (a_1 , a_2 , a_3 , and a_4) by varying the values of r_{Si} and shown in panel (d) of Fig. 7.

Fig. 7: Panel (a) shows the ED resonance response in scattering spectrum of Si-WS₂ (3L). The plots are constructed by varying the values of r_{Si} from 90 nm to 115 nm. To understand the coupling between ED-exciton, AM-exciton, uncoupled ED and uncoupled AM, we have plotted separately the scattering spectrum with $r_{Si} = 90$ nm (blue), 95 nm (green), 110 nm (red), 115 nm (black), as shown in panel (b) respectively. Panel (c) shows a color-map of ED contribution in Q_{sca} as a function of energy and r_{Si} , which confirm the anti-crossing behavior. Panel (d) shows the peak positions of the simulated scattering spectra, where the resonant energy values of the hybrid modes are extracted from panel (a) of Fig. 7.

Here the resonant energies are extracted from panel (a) of Fig. 7 and the energy difference between UEB and LEB is represented by Rabi splitting energy, shown as black arrow in panel (d). The features and nature of this plot are quite similar like 1L-WS₂ (panel (d) of Fig. 6), while the values of the Rabi splitting energy are different. The main conclusions that can be drawn from these figures are the following. First of all the anti-crossing behavior reflects the strong coupling nature upon the energy exchange via light-matter interaction for Si-3L WS₂ heterostructure. Then larger Rabi splitting energy values are observed for 3L WS₂ in contrast with 1L WS₂, while the remaining properties are almost similar in the case of 1L and 3L WS₂.

Conclusions

In this study, we conducted a thorough numerical analysis of the hybrid Mie-exciton modes originating from the Si-WS₂ heterostructure. Through our simulations, we treated the Si-WS₂ heterostructure as an isolated spherical core-shell nanostructure. Our investigations revealed compelling evidence of resonance coupling between distinct Mie active modes from the Si nanosphere and excitons from the WS₂ monolayer. The resulting mode hybridization led to the formation of UEB and LEB, demonstrating energy transfer due to the symmetry between modes during light-matter interactions [33]. To further assess the strength of coupling between modes, we employed the classical coupled oscillator model and calculated Hopfield coefficients, affirming the presence of strong coupling. Anti-crossing behavior observed between different modes provided solid confirmation of the strong coupling phenomenon. Furthermore, we examined the influence of varying the number of WS₂ monolayers and the size of the Si nano-resonator on mode hybridization and resonance coupling. Our calculation predicts that the coupling between MQ-exciton exhibited a Rabi splitting energy of approximately 50 meV for 1L of WS₂, which further increased to around 80 meV for an increased number of monolayers (3L). A similar trend of different Rabi splitting energy values was observed for the coupling of ED-exciton and AM-exciton.

Notably, the coupling strength and coherent energy transfer between modes proved highly sensitive to both the number of WS_2 monolayers and the size of the Si nano-resonator.

It is worth mentioning that, for both 1L and 3L Si- WS_2 heterostructures, AM and ED become entirely uncoupled during the ED-exciton and AM-exciton coupling, respectively. Additionally, we observed that ED-exciton coupling predominated for smaller Si nanospheres, while an increase in the size of the Si nanosphere favored AM-exciton coupling. Our findings also extended to other scenarios involving high refractive index spherical nano-core coated with 2D-TMDC or van der Waals materials, underscoring the broader applicability of our results beyond Si and WS_2 . We anticipate that our research outcomes will not only benefit the understanding of polariton-exciton nanodevices but also prove valuable for diverse quantum technology-based applications. The insights gained from this study may pave the way for innovative advancements in the design and development of nanophotonic devices and hold promise for future research endeavors in this exciting field.

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Graphical abstract

